

Synthesis, crystal structures and magnetic properties of two cyanide-bridged one-dimensional single chain M^{II} - Mn^{II} ($M = Ni, Pd$) complexes

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Manuscript received online 01 February 2017, accepted 23 February 2017

Abstract : Two cyanide-bridged heterobimetallic M^{II} - Mn^{II} ($M = Ni, Pd$) complexes have been prepared by assembling the mononuclear seven-coordinated closed macrocycle manganese(II) compound and the tetracyanometallic building blocks. Single X-ray diffraction analysis show that these two complexes $[Mn(L^1)][M(CN)_4]$ ($M = Ni$ (1), Pd (2); $L^1 = 3,6$ -diazaoctane-1,8-diamine) present predictable one-dimensional single chain structures. The molecular structures of the one-dimensional complexes consists of alternating units of $[Mn(L^1)]^{2+}$ and $[M(CN)_4]^{2-}$, forming a cyanide-bridged neutral polymeric chain. The coordination geometry of manganese(II) ion in the two complexes is a slightly distorted pentagonal-bipyrimidal with two cyanide nitrogen atoms at the *trans* positions and N_5 coordinating mode at the equatorial plane from the macrocyclic ligand. The magnetic properties for these two complexes were investigated and the results showed the very weak antiferromagnetic coupling between neighboring Mn^{II} ions connected by the diamagnetic tetra-cyanometallic building block. A best-fit to the magnetic susceptibility leads to the magnetic coupling constants $J = -0.09$ and -0.12 cm^{-1} for complexes 1 and 2, respectively.

Keywords : Cyanide-bridged, 1D complex, crystal structure, magnetic property.

Introduction

During the past three decades, the design and synthesis of molecular magnetic materials has been given extensive attention due to their potential application in several scientific fields¹⁻⁵, including chemistry, physics, materials and biology, etc. Recently, due to the interesting magnetic properties, such as single molecular magnet (SMM)⁶⁻¹⁹ and single chain magnet (SCM)²⁰⁻²⁸, which are with great potential in the field of information storage, the design and synthesis of low-dimensional cyanide-bridged magnetic complexes has attracted much interest. Generally, the rational tuning the structure of the cyanide-bridged magnetic complexes can be fulfilled by carefully considering the following several factors coming from the cyanide-containing building block, including the number and the position of cyanide group, the number and the nature of charge of the cyanide-containing building block, and the steric effect of the reactants, etc.²⁹⁻³⁵.

On the other hand, the ancillary ligands attached to the counterpart assembling cations used to assemble with various polycyanometallates also play a crucial role for constructing cyanide-bridged complexes with different structures. Macrocyclic ligands (mac), which are usually coordinated to the equatorial plane of the metal ions and with two *trans* replaceable sites being occupied by other ligands, can be used as good ancillary ligands to effectively lower the dimensionality of the complex formed. The Mn^{II} compounds based-on the two notable macrocyclic ligands with high structural similarity (Scheme 1) have been proven good candidates for synthesis of cyanide-bridged magnetic complexes with low-dimensional structures and interesting magnetic properties³⁶⁻⁴³. Our very recent work show that the $[Mn(L^1)]^{2+}$ ($L^1 = 3,6$ -diazaoctane-1,8-diamine) is inclined to form cyanide-bridged one-dimensional infinite structure, while $[Mn(L^2)]^{2+}$ ($L^2 = 3,6$ -dioxaoctano-1,8-diamine) is more favor of constructing polynuclear entity⁴⁴. Following this idea, we

purposefully investigated the reactions of $[\text{Mn}(\text{L}^1)]^{2+}$ with two tetra-cyanomatalates, and obtained two one-dimensional cyanide-bridged M (M = Ni, Pd)-Mn complexes, which further testify that fact that this assemble segment is willing to form target complexes with infinite structure. The two one-dimensional chain complexes with the formula $[\text{Mn}(\text{L}^1)][\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_4]$ (**1**) and $[\text{Mn}(\text{L}^1)][\text{Pd}(\text{CN})_4]$ (**2**), including their synthesis, crystal structures and magnetic properties, will be described in this paper.

Scheme 1. The two notable macrocyclic manganese(II) compounds reported for assembling cyanide-bridged magnetic complexes.

Experimental

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were carried out with an Elementary Vario El. The infrared spectroscopy on KBr pellets was performed on a Magna-IR 750 spectrophotometer in the 4000–400 cm^{-1} region. Variable-temperature magnetic susceptibility and field dependence magnetization measurements were performed on a Quantum Design MPMS SQUID magnetometer. The experimental susceptibilities were corrected for the diamagnetism of the constituent atoms (Pascal's tables).

General procedures and materials : All the reactions were carried out under an air atmosphere and all chemicals and solvents used were reagent grade without further purification. $[\text{Mn}(\text{L}^1)(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]\text{ClO}_4$ was available from the previous work⁴².

Synthesis of the complexes **1** and **2** :

A solution containing $\text{K}_2[\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_4]$ (0.1 mmol, 24.1 mg) or $\text{K}_2[\text{Pd}(\text{CN})_4]$ (0.1 mmol, 28.8 mg) dissolved in 5 ml H_2O was laid in the bottom of a tube, upon

which a mixture solvent of water and methanol with a ratio of 1 : 1 was carefully added. Then, a solution of $[\text{Mn}(\text{L}^1)(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]\text{ClO}_4$ (48.1 mg, 0.1 mmol) in 5 ml CH_3OH was carefully added to the top of the mixture solvent layer above formed. About two weeks later, single yellow crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained from the interface, collected by filtration and dried in air. Yield : 82.8 mg, 56.1%. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{57}\text{H}_{71}\text{Mn}_3\text{N}_{27}\text{Ni}_3$: C, 46.40; H, 4.85; N, 25.64. Found : C, 46.48; H, 4.90; N, 25.41; Main IR bands (cm^{-1}) : 2160, 2123 (s, $\nu\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$), 1620~1630 (vs, $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$).

Complex 2 : Yield : 97.2 mg, 60.1%. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{57}\text{H}_{71}\text{Mn}_3\text{N}_{27}\text{Pd}_3$: C, 42.30; H, 4.42; N, 23.37. Found : C, 42.18; H, 4.24; N, 23.51; IR bands (cm^{-1}) : 2158, 2125 (s, $\nu\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$), 1620~1630 (vs, $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$).

X-Ray data collection and structure refinement :

Crystal data and structure refinement details for complexes **1** and **2** are listed in Table 1. Crystal data were collected on a Bruker SMART CCD diffractometer with a $\text{MoK}\alpha$ sealed tube ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) at 293 K, using a ω scan mode. The structure was solved by a combination of direct method and heavy atom method using SHELXL97⁴⁵. All the nonhydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic displacement coefficients. For the disordered content, the partially occupied atom was refined isotropically. Hydrogen atoms were assigned isotropic displacement coefficients $U(\text{H}) = 1.2U(\text{C})$ or $1.5U(\text{C})$ and their coordinates were allowed to ride on their respective carbons using SHELXL97. CCDC 1524396 and 1524397 for these two complexes contain the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and general characterization :

A series of reported works^{36–43} proved that the 15-membered pentadentate macrocycles 3,6-diazaoctane-1,8-diamine and 3,6-dioxaoctano-1,8-diamine, which adapt a planar conformation and therefore impose a pentagonal-based geometry on the central metal ion with different electronic configuration,

Table 1. Crystallographic data for complexes **1** and **2**

	1	2
Chemical formula	C ₅₇ H ₇₁ Mn ₃ N ₂₇ Ni ₃	C ₅₇ H ₇₁ Mn ₃ N ₂₇ Pd ₃
Fw	1475.32	1618.43
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Monoclinic
Space group	C2/c	C2/c
<i>a</i> (Å)	32.943(9)	33.411(14)
<i>b</i> (Å)	11.724(3)	11.752(5)
<i>c</i> (Å)	20.400(6)	20.564(9)
α (deg)	90	90
β (deg)	122.408(4)	121.451(6)
γ (deg)	90	90
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	6652(3)	6888(5)
<i>Z</i>	4	4
Completeness	99.3%	98.8%
<i>F</i> (000)	3024	3260
Reflections/ collected/unique	15987/5811/3266	16425/5991/3054
Data/restraints/ parameters	5811/0/416	5991/0/412
θ (deg)	1.89–25.01	1.87–25.01
GOF	1.354	1.028
<i>R</i> ₁ [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	0.1304	0.0728
<i>wR</i> ₂ (all data)	0.3025	0.1883
Largest diff. peak and hole (e/Å ³)	2.746 and –0.744	3.033 and –0.671

are good auxiliary ligands for stabilization of seven-coordinated species. Due to the large steric effect from the equatorial direction of the macrocyclic ligand and the existence of two weakly bonded and replaceable ligands at the two *trans* positions, the Mn^{II} compounds based-on the above two macrocycle ligands are excellent precursors for the design and synthesis of low-dimensional complexes. The reactions of the manganese(II) compound [Mn(L¹)]²⁺ with square tetracyanide-containing building block have been carried out, resulting in two cyanide-bridged heterobimetallic complexes with one-dimensional structures.

The two cyanide-bridged complexes have been characterized by IR spectra. In the IR spectra of complexes **1** and **2**, two sharp peaks due to the cyanide-stretching vibration were observed at about 2125 and 2160 cm⁻¹, respectively, indicating the presence of bridging and nonbridging cyanide ligands in these complexes.

The crystal structure description of the complexes 1 and 2 :

The selected bond lengths and angles for complexes **1** and **2** are given in Table 2. The representative asymmetry neutral binuclear unit, one-dimensional chain structure and the representative cell packing diagram for these two complexes are shown in Figs. 1–3, respectively.

As can be found in Table 1 and Fig. 2, these two isostructural complexes crystallizing in monoclinic space group C2/c, possess very similar 1D chain structure. The infinite chain structure is constructed by the repeated [-NC-M(CN)₂-CN-Mn(L¹)-] units, in which the tetracyanide-containing building block, acting as a bidentate ligand through its two cyanide groups, connects the Mn^{II} ion of two independent macrocyclic manganese units. The M atom involved in a square conformation is coordinated by four C atoms of the four cyanide groups with almost equal bond parameters, indicating that coordinating or non-coordinating of the N atom to the metal atom has no obvious influence on the geometry of the cyanide precursor.

The coordination sphere of the Mn^{II} ion in complexes **1** and **2** is a slightly distorted pentagonal-bipyrimidal, in which the five equatorial positions are occupied by N₅ unit coming from the macrocyclic ligand and two axial ones coordinated by two N atoms of cyanide groups. The distances between Mn ion and equatorial N atoms (Table 2), are in good agreement with those found in its precursors⁴⁶. The average Mn-

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°) for complexes **1** and **2**

	1 (M = Ni)	2 (M = Pd)
Mn(1)-N(1)	2.258(7)	2.266(7)
Mn(1)-N(3)	2.226(8)	2.243(8)
Mn(1)-N(4)	2.259(8)	2.287(8)
Mn(1)-N(5)	2.336(9)	2.339(7)
Mn(1)-N(6)	2.351(7)	2.307(8)
Mn(1)-N(7)	2.287(8)	2.294(7)
Mn(1)-N(8)	2.267(7)	2.271(7)
M(1)-C(1)	1.849(8)	1.981(9)
M(1)-C(2)	1.866(11)	1.988(10)
C(1)-N(1)-Mn(1)	151.6(7)	151.3(7)
N(1)-C(1)-M(1)	178.0(8)	178.7(8)

N_{cyanide} bond lengths in these two complexes are 2.263 and 2.269 Å, respectively, basically consistent with the average $Mn-N_{\text{equatorial}}$ bond length about 2.294 Å. As tabulated in Table 2, the $M-C\equiv N$ bond angles are

very close to 180° , indicating that these three atoms are in a very good linear conformation, while $Mn-N\equiv C$ units in the two complexes are obvious bent only with the values of $151.6(7)$ and $151.3(7)^\circ$, respectively.

Magnetic properties of complexes 1 and 2 :

The temperature dependence of magnetic susceptibility for these two complexes is measured in the temperature range of 2–300 K under the applied field of 2000 Oe (Fig. 4). The room temperature $\chi_m T$ values for complexes 1 and 2 are 4.32 and 4.30 emu K mol^{-1} , respectively, basically agreement with the spin only value of 4.375 emu K mol^{-1} for the isolated high spin Mn^{II} ($S = 5/2$). The $\chi_m T$ value remains almost constant from 300 to about 40 K, and after this, the $\chi_m T$ value starts to decrease rapidly and reaches the lowest value of about 2.75 emu K mol^{-1} at 2 K. The mag-

Fig. 1. The representative neutral binuclear independent unit of complexes 1 and 2. All the hydrogen atoms have been omitted for clarity.

Fig. 2. The representative 1D structure of complexes 1 and 2. All the hydrogen atoms have been omitted for clarity.

Fig. 3. The representative cell packing diagram for complexes 1 and 2 along a axis. All the hydrogen atoms have been omitted for clarity.

Fig. 4. Temperature dependence of $\chi_m T$ and χ_m^{-1} of complexes **1** (left) and **2** (right).
(The solid line represents the best fit based on the parameters discussed in the text).

netic susceptibility conforms well to Curie-Weiss law in a range of 2–300 K (the inset of Fig. 4) and give the negative Weiss constant $\theta = -0.52$ K and Curie constant $C = 4.33$ emu K mol⁻¹ for complex **1** and $\theta = -0.98$ K and Curie constant $C = 4.31$ emu K mol⁻¹ for complex **2**. These results primarily show the anti-ferromagnetic magnetic coupling between the two Mn^{II} centers bridged by [-NC-M(CN)₂-CN-] unit in these two complexes.

The magnetic data are analyzed by using the Hamiltonian: $\hat{H} = -2\Sigma J\hat{S}_i\hat{S}_{i+1}$. The temperature dependence of the magnetic susceptibility is given by the equation^{47,48}:

$$\chi_M^{\text{chain}} = Ng^2\beta^2\{S_{\text{Mn}}(S_{\text{Mn}} + 1)/3KT\}((1 + \mu)/(1 - \mu))$$

(Fisher's infinite chain model) with:

$$\mu = \coth [JS_{\text{Mn}}(S_{\text{Mn}} + 1)/KT] - [KT/JS_{\text{Mn}}(S_{\text{Mn}} + 1)]$$

The least-squares fit to the data leads to $J = -0.09$ cm⁻¹, $g = 1.99$, $R = 1.12 \times 10^{-5}$ and $J = -0.19$ cm⁻¹, $g = 1.99$, $R = 2.34 \times 10^{-5}$ for complexes **1** and **2**, respectively. The small J value, which is comparable to the coupling values between the Mn^{II} ions bridged by the diamagnetic cyanide precursors in other complexes⁴³, suggests the overall very weak magnetic coupling between the Mn^{II} ions with a long separation.

Conclusion

In summary, two heterobimetallic cyanide-bridged M^{II}-Mn^{II} (M = Ni, Pd) one-dimensional single chain

complexes have been rationally designed and successfully synthesized by using the tetra-cyanide-metallic building blocks and the seven-coordinated macrocyclic Mn^{II} compounds. The present result in combination with the very recent report⁴⁴ further confirm the fact that this manganese(II) segment is more favor of forming cyanide-bridged complexes with one-dimensional chain structures. The magnetic studies demonstrate the weak antiferromagnetic interaction between the Mn^{II} ions through the diamagnetic cyanide precursor in the three reported complexes.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the Natural Science Foundation of China (21171107 and 21671121).

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